

TO DETERMINE THE EFFICACY OF CAUDAL BLOCK COMBINED WITH GENERAL ANAESTHESIA ON INTRA-OPERATIVE HEMODYNAMIC STABILITY THAN GENERAL ANAESTHESIA ALONE IN PEDIATRIC PATIENTS.

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: The infants and children are unable to communicate and describe the pain intensity and inappropriate bodily responses to pain in children can impact a variety of hormonal, metabolic, immunological, and psychiatric conditions, endangering the physical and mental growth of children⁽¹⁾. Caudal block with general anaesthesia in children can cause better hemodynamic stability intra-operatively, decreased drug requirements and better post-operative pain relief leading to the early rehabilitation and recovery of children.

MATERIAL AND METHODS: Total 20 patients were enrolled in this comparative study with inclusion criteria of age group between 2-5 yrs., scheduled for elective infra-umbilical surgeries. They were randomly divided into 2 groups. Group A received general anaesthesia with caudal block and group B received general anaesthesia. Intra-operative Hemodynamic Stability, post-operative complications and post-operative pain relief was recorded.

RESULTS: Results were calculated in the form of percentage, mean, standard deviation. The demographic data was comparable in both the groups. General anaesthesia with caudal block had lower blood pressure and heart rate changes intra-operatively than general anaesthesia alone ($p \leq 0.05$). pain score was significantly lower in general anaesthesia with caudal block group which suggests better early post-operative pain control. However, General anaesthesia group showed significantly shorter recovery time post-operatively compared to general anaesthesia with caudal block group as there is analgesic effect of caudal block leading to inhibition of pain stimulus causing delayed awakening, also general anaesthesia with caudal block group showed longer time before rescue analgesia was needed ($p=0.000$).

CONCLUSION: General Anaesthesia along with Caudal block provides better intra-operative hemodynamic stability and excellent post-operative pain relief than General Anaesthesia alone in pediatric age group.

KEYWORD

Caudal block, intra-operative hemodynamic stability, faster recovery, pediatric anaesthesia, analgesic efficacy, pain management in children.

INTRODUCTION

Stress in children is most frequently caused by pain due to surgical stimulation. Consequently, it needs to be properly assessed and cared for both during and after surgery. The primary function of analgesics and local anesthetics used in regional anesthesia is to modulate and suppress the stress response to surgical trauma⁽¹⁾. The infants and children are unable to communicate and describe the pain intensity and inappropriate bodily responses to pain in children can impact a variety of hormonal, metabolic, immunological, and psychiatric conditions, endangering the physical and mental growth of children⁽²⁾. Thus, it is important to provide good analgesia intra-operatively and post-operatively.

Caudal anaesthesia is one of the most common regional anaesthesia techniques used in children to provide intra-operative and post-operative analgesia for infra-umbilical surgeries. It can be used as sole technique for infra-umbilical procedures or be used along with general anaesthesia in children. Caudal anaesthesia is most frequently used in children along with general anaesthesia due to specific circumstances like their age and inability to cooperate during the procedures.⁽¹⁾ Caudal anaesthesia provides a safe approach to the epidural space in children. Studies have shown that combining Caudal block with general anaesthesia in children can cause better hemodynamic stability intra-operatively, decreased drug requirements and better post-operative pain relief leading to the early rehabilitation of children.

The infra-umbilical surgeries most common encountered in children are hypospadias repair, circumcision, herniotomy, appendicectomy, orthopaedic procedures like correction of lower limb deformities like club foot, congenital dislocation of hip, soft tissue release in cerebral palsy.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

AIM

To determine the efficacy of Caudal block combined with General anaesthesia on intra-operative hemodynamic stability than General anaesthesia alone in pediatric patients.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the hemodynamic stability in children when given Caudal anaesthesia along with general anaesthesia.
2. To study the effect of Caudal anaesthesia in children for post-operative pain management.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

STUDY DESIGN: Comparative interventional study

STUDY PERIOD: 04 MONTHS

STUDY POPULATION: Pediatric patients in age group of 2-5yrs posted in tertiary care center for infra-umbilical surgeries.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. ASA grade I and II patients
2. Age group of 2-5 years
3. Patients posted for elective infra-umbilical surgeries

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Parental denial for consent
2. Skin infection at a site of caudal block
3. Coagulopathies in children
4. Children having Congenital deformities
5. History of drug sensitivity
6. ASA grade III and IV

SAMPLE SIZE:

Calculated by the OpenEpi, version 3, open source sample calculator.

SAMPLE TECHNIQUE

Simple random sampling

METHODS

The study was conducted in a tertiary care hospital after the clearance from the Institutional Ethical Committee. All the parents of the patients participating in the study were informed in detail about the purpose of the study in their language. The written informed consent was taken from the parents of the patient participating in the study.

We studied total 20 patients who were admitted for infra-umbilical surgeries and were divided into two groups of 10 patients each by simple random sampling technique. Group A having 10 patients receiving general anaesthesia along with Caudal anaesthesia and Group B having 10 patients receiving General anaesthesia.

All the patients were examined and pre-anaesthetic check-up and the relevant investigations were done prior to surgery. Patients were kept nil by mouth for 6 hours prior to surgery.

GROUP A (GA+CA): INDUCTION

An IV line was secured with 24G IV cannula and IV infusion of Isolyte- P was started according to the weight of the patient. All these patients received premedication with inj. Ondansetron 0.1 mg/kg, inj. Glycopyrrolate 0.004mg/kg, inj. Midazolam 0.03mg/kg and inj. Fentanyl 2mcg/kg. Patients were preoxygenated with 100% O₂ with facemasks.

Induction was done with inj. Propofol 2mg/kg and inj. Atracurium 0.5mg/kg was given as a muscle relaxant after the loss of eyelash reflex. Laryngoscopy was then performed and patients were intubated with the appropriate size of endotracheal tube. Patients were maintained on O₂, N₂O and Sevoflurane. Incremental doses of inj. Atracurium 0.1mg/kg were given.

Patients were placed in left lateral decubitus position and the back of patient was painted and draped under all aseptic conditions. Confirmation of bony landmarks was done. After identifying the midline, the sacral hiatus was palpated as a depression between two sacral cornua. After identifying the sacral hiatus, the hiatus was punctured with the 21G needle inserted at angle of 45 degree from the skin until the giveaway sensation is felt. This giveaway feeling is secondary to piercing of Sacro-coccygeal ligament. After confirmation, inj. Bupivacaine 0.25% (P) 1ml/kg was injected.

After completion of surgery, patient was reversed from the muscle relaxant by inj. Glycopyrrolate 0.008mg/kg and inj. Neostigmine 0.05mg/kg IV slowly.

GROUP B(GA): INDUCTION

An IV line was secured with 24G IV cannula and IV infusion of Isolyte- P was started according to the weight of the patient. All these patients received premedication with inj. Ondansetron 0.1 mg/kg, inj. Glycopyrrolate 0.004mg/kg, inj. Midazolam 0.03mg/kg and inj. Fentanyl 2mcg/kg. Patients were preoxygenated with 100% O₂ with facemasks.

Induction was done with inj. Propofol 2mg/kg and inj. Atracurium 0.5mg/kg was given as a muscle relaxant after the loss of eyelash reflex. Laryngoscopy was then performed and patients were intubated with the appropriate size of endotracheal tube. Patients were maintained on O₂, N₂O and Sevoflurane. Incremental doses of inj. Atracurium 0.1mg/kg were given.

Intra-operatively the Non-invasive blood pressure, saturation, pulse rate of the patients was recorded every 15 minutes. Post-operative pain was assessed by the Wong-Baker faces pain scale. Time for rescue analgesia needed was recorded and in case of pain, inj. Paracetamol 15mg/kg IV was given. The total requirement of systemic analgesics was noted. The duration of anaesthesia, duration of caudal block, total requirement of all analgesics, complications and side effects of the drugs were observed and documented.

VARIABLES

Intra-operatively HR, BP, SPO₂ were monitored every 15 minutes for hemodynamic stability.

Post- operatively, pain score with Wong Baker Faces scale were observed every 2 hourly. Any complications post-operatively were noted.

RESULTS

The data were analyzed using IBM SPSS 22.0 software. Characteristics were compared between the two groups using student's t test for continuous variable and chi square test for categorical variables. When the expected count was less than 5. Fisher's exact test was used. P- value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant difference.

Table 1: Demographic data of children

Demographic Variables	Group A (n=10), n (%)	Group B (n=10), n (%)
Age (years)	3.10 \pm 1.022	3.45 \pm 0.927
Weight (kgs)	14.40 \pm 2.99	15.60 \pm 3.77
Height (cms)	95.30 \pm 7.353	97.25 \pm 5.574
Sex		
Female	3 (30)	2 (20)
Male	7 (70)	8 (80)
ASA Grade		
I	7 (70)	7 (70)
II	3 (30)	3 (30)

Table 2: Hemodynamic data intraoperatively

Variables	Group A (n=10), n (%)	Group B (n=10), n (%)	P – value
Blood Pressure – SBP			
Immediately after induction	97.50 ± 5.017	108.20 ± 7.67	0.002*
15 mins	95.70 ± 8.166	115.80 ± 12.44	0.000*
30 mins	95.20 ± 7.223	132.10 ± 7.05	0.000*
45 mins	93.90 ± 5.131	118.80 ± 12.09	0.000*
60mins	99.80 ± 5.750	121.80 ± 14.18	0.000*
Blood Pressure – DBP			
Immediately after induction	57.30±3.653	65.70 ± 6.06	0.001*
15 mins	58.30 ± 5.519	77.90 ± 4.75	0.000*
30 mins	55.80 ± 3.795	83.10 ± 7.20	0.000*
45 mins	61.70 ± 6.056	76.90 ± 4.6	0.000*
60mins	99.80 ± 5.750	71.60 ± 6.20	0.001*
HR			
Immediately after induction	114.20 ± 7.36	133.00 ± 12.94	0.001*
15 mins	107.70 ± 6.38	131.80 ± 12.59	0.000*
30 mins	111.80 ± 10.48	130.80 ± 14.40	0.003*
45 mins	111.00 ± 6.53	135.60 ± 17.82	0.001*
60mins	110.60 ± 6.67	120.20 ± 17.68	0.126
Saturation			
Immediately after induction	99.00 ± 0.817	99.70 ± 0.483	0.031*
15 mins	99.30 ± 0.483	99.60 ± 0.699	0.279
30 mins	99.70 ± 0.483	99.90 ± 0.316	0.288
45 mins	99.30 ± 0.675	99.70 ± 0.483	0.145
60mins	99.30 ± 0.675	99.60 ± 0.516	0.279

(*p value ≤ 0.05 indicate significance)

Comparison of Variables Over Time Between Group A and Group B

Fig 1: Hemodynamic Data Intraoperatively

Table 3: Comparison of Pain using Baker Faces Scale

Parameter	Group A (n=10), n (%)	Group B (n=10), n (%)	P – value
Immediately after Surgery	2.70 ± 1.16	6.60 ± 1.65	0.000*
2 hours	2.80 ± 1.03	6.20 ± 1.14	0.000*
4 hours	3.60 ± 0.84	5.60 ± 1.27	0.001*
6 hours	5.00 ± 1.41	6.80 ± 1.03	0.004*
8 hours	7.00 ± 1.05	7.20 ± 1.03	0.673
10 hours	8.40 ± 0.84	8.40 ± 1.27	1.00

Fig 2: Pain Scale

Fig 3: Complications

Table 4: Comparison of side effects

Parameter	Group A (n=10), n (%)	Group B (n=10), n (%)	P – value
Nausea/vomiting	2 (20%)	4 (40%)	0.628
Hypotension	5 (50%)	2 (20%)	0.350
Tachycardia	1 (10%)	5 (50%)	0.141

Table 5: Parameters

	Group A (n=10), n (%)	Group B (n=10), n (%)	P-value
Duration of Anaesthesia(mins)	56±4.05	36.2±6.67	0.035
Duration of Surgery(mins)	47.6±8.6	40.3±9.06	0.37
Recovery time(mins)	19.2 ± 3.48	17.40 ± 3.69	0.2
Duration of Caudal block(mins)	281.00 ± 41.82	NA	
Time for rescue analgesia(mins)	250.00 ± 41.10	36.10 ± 9.4	0.000*

Fig 4: Other Parameters

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents comparable demographic data for Group A and Group B, each with 10 children. The mean age, weight, and height are similar between groups, indicating both the groups were demographically comparable. Gender distribution shows a male predominance in both groups (70% in Group A and 80% in Group B) as most of the infra-umbilical surgeries are male gender specific like circumcision, hydrocele, testicular torsion etc. ASA grade distribution is similar, with 70% in Grade I and 30% in Grade II, reflecting comparable health statuses.

Table 2: Group B showed significantly higher systolic and diastolic blood pressure (SBP, DBP) and heart rate (HR) compared to Group A at most time points ($p \leq 0.05$). This is the result of lumbar preganglionic sympathetic inhibition due to caudal block given in group A.

Table 3: Pain scores assessed using the Baker Faces Scale showed significantly lower pain in Group A compared to Group B immediately after surgery and up to 6 hours postoperatively ($p \leq 0.05$) due to the intervention done in group A. At 8 and 10 hours, both groups reported similar pain levels, with no significant difference ($p=0.673, 1.00$). This suggests Group A had better early postoperative pain control.

Table 4: The incidence of side effects was compared between Group A and Group B. Nausea/vomiting occurred in 20% of Group A and 40% of Group B ($p=0.628$). Hypotension was more common in Group A (50%) than Group B (20%) ($p=0.350$). Tachycardia was more frequent in Group B (50%) compared to Group A (10%) ($p=0.141$). None of the differences were statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 5: There is a statistically significant difference between Group A and Group B. Group A experienced a longer duration of anaesthesia compared to Group B. The difference in duration of surgery between the groups is not statistically significant, indicating that the surgical duration is comparable across both groups. However, Group B showed significantly shorter recovery time postoperatively compared to group A as there is analgesic effect of caudal block leading to inhibition of pain stimulus in group A which leads to delayed awakening from general anaesthesia, and it also showed longer time before rescue analgesia was needed ($p=0.000$). The duration of the caudal block was 281 minutes in Group A, a factor not applicable to Group B. These findings highlight better postoperative pain management in Group A.

CONCLUSION

General Anaesthesia along with Caudal block provides better intra-operative hemodynamic stability and excellent post-operative pain relief than General Anaesthesia alone in pediatric age group.

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